

Family Adjustment to Hereditary Cancer Syndromes: A Systematic Review

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Abstract

Hereditary cancer syndromes are inherited genetic pathogenic variants that significantly increase the risk of developing cancer. When an individual becomes aware of their increased probability of having cancer, the whole family is affected by this new reality and needs to adjust. However, adjustment to hereditary cancer syndromes has been mainly studied at an individual level and research about familial adjustment remains dispersed and disorganized. To overcome this gap, this review aims to understand how families adjust to genetic testing and risk management, and to what extent the adjustment of the family influences the psychological response and risk management behaviors of mutation carriers. We conducted searches on the PubMed/Med Line, PsycInfo, SCOPUS, and Google Scholar databases and used the Mixed Methods Appraisal Tool (MMAT-v2018) to assess the methodological quality of each selected study. Thirty studies met the inclusion criteria. Most Results highlighted the interdependent nature of adjustment of pathogenic variant carriers and their families. The way carriers adjust to the syndrome is highly related with how family members react to it, particularly partners and siblings. Couples who share their worries and communicate openly about cancer risk present a better long-term adjustment than couples who use protective buffering (not talking about it to avoid disturbing the partner) or emotional distancing. Parents need help dealing with disclosing genetic information to their children. These findings reinforce the importance of adopting a family-centered approach in the context of genetic counseling and the necessity of involving family members in research.

Keywords: hereditary cancer syndromes, genetic testing, family adjustment, cancer risk management, decision-making, genetic counseling

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Introduction

Nearly five to ten percent of all cancers are hereditary and caused by inherited pathogenic variants that significantly increase lifetime risk of cancer relative to the general population [1]. To identify if an individual carries a pathogenic variant that increases risk of cancer, geneticists may prescribe genetic tests for cancer susceptibility to individuals from hereditary cancer families [2,3]. When a healthy individual is identified as a pre-symptomatic pathogenic variant carrier, cancer risk may be reduced through enhanced surveillance procedures (e.g., regular colonoscopies), pharmacy chemoprevention, and/or prophylactic surgeries (e.g., mastectomies) [4,5]. Additionally, family planning solutions, such as medically assisted reproduction, may be offered to prevent future children from carrying the pathogenic variant [6]. However, although being able to prevent cancer onset is crucial for pathogenic variant carriers, knowing about future cancer risk, deciding on the personal prevention plan, and adapting to risk-reduction measures pose significant psychological challenges [7–11]. In fact, deciding if, how, and when to undergo the invasive medical procedures usually reserved for these situations [4,12] may not only elicit distress in the pathogenic variant carriers [13] but also in their family members [14].

Therefore, the aftermath of a positive genetic testing result commonly represents a critical event for the whole family [15]. Not only it has the potential to impact the health of family members who may also be carrying the pathogenic variant but may also affect family members' relationships and couple's reproductive decisions [16,17]. In addition, genetic testing uptake is usually carried out in a cascading way [18], which often means that the new pathogenic variant carriers vicariously experience the outcome of their carrier relatives' decisions [14]. In this sense, dealing with the uncertainty of possible future losses without

abdicating from important life cycle goals (e.g., having children) requires pathogenic variant carriers and their family members to develop great flexibility in an inter-related adjustment process [19,20]. In other words, to understand the psychological adjustment to inherited cancer risk, one must conceive it as a systemic phenomenon [19–21].

Previous systematic reviews have already summarized the existing knowledge on the psychological adjustment of the applicant to genetic testing and counseling [22–28] and on the effectiveness of interventions to help pathogenic variant carrier health-related decision-making processes [29]. However, studies on familial adjustment in the face of inherited genetic syndromes remain dispersed and disaggregated. To our knowledge, to date only one review [30] focused on the familial adjustment to hereditary cancer syndromes. Nevertheless, this contribution only explored the experiences of male partners of hereditary breast and ovarian cancer syndrome carriers.

With the aim of addressing this gap, the present systematic review organizes current knowledge on the topic of familial adjustment to hereditary cancer syndromes in a rigorous and replicable way. Our objective is to review findings from existing research investigating the psychological adjustment of the families of pre-symptomatic pathogenic variant carriers to an increased susceptibility to hereditary cancer. Specifically, we focused on the period following a positive genetic test, including the long-term adjustment to personalized prevention programs with the aim to understand: (1) how do families adjust to a positive genetic test result of a pre-symptomatic member and his/her risk management behaviors? (2) To what extent does the family influence the psychological adjustment and risk management behaviors of the pre-symptomatic pathogenic variant carrier?

Method

This systematic review was registered with PROSPERO (ID CRD42020142200). Data extraction, critical appraisal, and qualitative synthesis were in line with established systematic review and qualitative synthesis methods [31] and followed the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) statement [32].

Search strategy

We conducted searches in the following databases: PubMed/ MEDLINE, Scopus, PsycInfo, and Google Scholar between June 28th to July 2nd, 2019, which were updated between the 13th and 17th of January 2020, and again between June 23rd and July 2nd, 2021 and complemented with hand-searching. The search strategies combined key terms and Medical Search Headings (MESH) terms for the concepts of inherited cancer risk, unaffected pathogenic variant carrier, emotional distress, family psychosocial adjustment and risk management behavior, and personalized preventive programs, following the PICO elements [33]. Boolean and truncation operators were used to combine search terms more systematically and to list documents containing variations on search terms, respectively [34]. We modified the search syntax as appropriate for each database.

Inclusion and exclusion criteria

We only included articles that: 1) were original studies, 2) described the psychosocial adjustment of the family system of pre-symptomatic pathogenic variant carriers to inherited cancer risk test and/or personalized preventive programs; 3) investigated at least one measure of psychological adjustment (e.g. emotional distress, quality of life, anxiety, depression, anger) to genetic testing results or risk management behaviors of carrier's family members; 4) investigated family barriers and facilitators of decision making and adherence to personalized preventive programs/risk management behaviors. Studies targeting families of either mixed populations (affected/unaffected) or currently unaffected individuals previously

diagnosed with cancer were included. We did not restrict publications based on the study design, ethnicity, or year of publication. The reason we opted to only include studies on pre-symptomatic pathogenic variant carriers was to better capture the experience of being and living with a pathogenic variant carrier, which may be different from that of being and living with a hereditary cancer patient. The methodological choice of not restricting studies by design methods aimed to aggregate all existing knowledge about the psychological adjustment of families to inherited cancer risk. Articles were excluded if 1) pre-symptomatic pathogenic variants carriers were under the age of 18 years; 2) considered only families of individuals not yet tested for inherited cancer risk; 3) considered families of affected (cancer patients) pathogenic variant carriers only; 4) considered only biomedical outcomes; 5) investigated only the psychosocial adjustment of pre-symptomatic pathogenic variant carriers, but not the one of their family members.

Study selection

Following the search and exclusion of duplicates, two reviewers (authors GP and VB) independently screened the eligibility of the articles first on the title and the abstract, and the full text according to the inclusion criteria. Authors CS and PMM resolved disagreements. Authors PG and CS conducted a separate search, by independently screening reference lists of previous systematic reviews [22–24,26,28,30,35], one doctoral thesis [36], and searching articles in relevant journals (e.g., American Journal of Human Genetics, European Journal of Human Genetics, Journal of Genetic Counselling, Journal of Community Genetics, Health Psychology, Psycho-Oncology). Search updates were conducted by author PG in 2020 and by authors PG and MN in 2021. Following Smith et al. [37], the review team included at least one person with methodological expertise in conducting systematic reviews (PG, GP, VB, CS, PMM) and at least two experts on the topic under review (CS, ES, EC, JS).

Searches of electronic databases identified 1,338 reports, and searches by hand identified 16 articles. From the 1,354 total records that were found, 20 were duplicates, and 1,289 records were excluded based on information from the title and abstract. The remaining 45 articles were evaluated for inclusion by reviewing their full text, and resulted in the exclusion of 18 records for the following reasons: (1) considered only the psychosocial adjustment of unaffected pathogenic variant carriers, but not of their families (n=9) [38–46]; (2) considered the psychological adjustment of families of individuals not yet tested for inherited cancer risk; (n=1) [47]; (3) did not report quantitative/qualitative outcomes (e.g., opinion, theoretical, perspective articles, etc.) (n=5) [48–52]; (4) pre-symptomatic pathogenic variant carriers were under the age of 18 (n=1) [53]; (5) study focuses more on the carrier’s type of communication than on the psychological impact of the genetic test results on his/her family/system (n=2) [54,55]. During the search update, 3 new articles were included [56–58]. References of the remaining 30 articles were further screened for relevant records, but none was found. The flowchart presented in Figure 1 provides step-by-step details of the study selection process.

Figure 1. PRISMA Flow-chart

Assessment of risk of bias

The mixed-methods appraisal tool (MMAT-v2018) [59] was used to assess the methodological quality of each selected study. The MMAT-v2018 includes a total of 25 criteria and two screening questions rated on a scale of yes, no, and cannot tell. The tool results in a methodological rating of 0 (0% lowest quality) to 5 (100%, highest quality) quality criteria met by

each study⁴⁸. The assessment was conducted independently by authors VB and GP, and any disagreements were resolved by a third author (PG, PMM, or CS). The ratings of each selected study are presented in Supplementary material 1 (S1).

Data extraction and synthesis

Authors GP and VB independently extracted the following data from included studies: first author and year of publication; country; the aim of the study; study design; study setting; study outcome; follow-up points, sample size, age of applicants; gender of the applicants; clinical status of the family member; the role of the member in the family; the family role of the pathogenic variant carriers; type of pathogenic variant/cancer; psychological/behavioral outcome(s) and measure; results; retention; barriers and facilitators. The results of selected studies were summarized, to provide a qualitative synthesis of the impact that genetic risk test positive results and risk management decisions have on the family psychosocial adjustment, and how the family influences the psychological response and risk management behaviors of both the pre-symptomatic pathogenic variant carrier and family members themselves.

Results

Description of the included studies: the MMAT-v2018 checklist

The distribution of MMAT-v2018 scores was generally high across study designs, with 22 out of 30 (73,3%) studies meeting 100% of quality criteria and eight records having 80% of quality criteria met (see Supplementary material 1). All qualitative studies (n=6)^{12,49–52} obtained the highest possible score, which was also achieved in 2 out of 6 (33,3%) quantitative non-randomized studies^{53,54} and 14 out of 18 (77,8%) records adopting a quantitative descriptive method^{55–66}. The only mixed-method study included in this review also met 100% of quality criteria⁶⁷. No quantitative randomized controlled trial was included.

Overview of characteristics of included articles

We identified 30 studies meeting inclusion criteria. Most of them (n = 17) were conducted in the USA, while five studies were carried out in the Netherlands [60–64], two in Canada [65,66] and another two in Australia [67,68], one in the United Kingdom [69], one in Portugal [57], one in France [58] and another one in Japan [70]. Twenty-one records focused only on hereditary breast and ovarian cancer syndrome (HBOC), four on hereditary non-polyposis colorectal cancer syndrome (HNPCC) [70–73], three studies comprised a sample of both HBOC and HNPCC pathogenic variant carriers [61,62,74], one study included HNPCC, HBOC, and hereditary diffuse gastric cancer syndrome (HDGC) pathogenic variant carriers [57] and one study regarded Familial Adenomatous Polyposis [75]. The sample size varied from a minimum of 17 participants (cumulative between pathogenic variant carriers and their family members) [76] to a maximum of 272 pathogenic variant carriers, only [61,62]. Carriers were all adults in the age range 20-50. Most studies investigated the experience of genetic testing in couple and sibling relationships. When referring to psychological adjustment, studies considered a variety of constructs, such as general and cancer-related distress, cancer worry, risk perception, depression, anxiety, and somatization. Most papers presented pre-post-testing studies conducted with pathogenic variant carriers, with post-testing typically measured six months after testing results. However, one study measured long-term adjustment up to 24 months after genetic testing results [77]. Six papers employed a qualitative research method conducted on pathogenic variant carriers and their family members [14,57,67,70,71,76] (Table 1).

The family system facing genetic testing results

Overall, family members experienced feelings of anguish, worry, and guilt after genetic testing results throughout the selected studies. More specifically, partners of pathogenic variant carriers reported psychological distress, anxiety [60,68,78,79], and worries about their spouse developing cancer and dying, as well as concerns about their children carrying the pathogenic variant [65]. Adult daughters of unaffected BRCA1/2 (a type of HBOC) carriers showed clinical levels of cancer-related distress and worries both toward their mothers and other relatives [80].

Moreover, pathogenic variant carriers disclosed feeling guilty for their children, and for their carrier siblings [62,70], while non-carrier HNPCC applicants declared feeling guilty towards relatives with hereditary cancer [70]. Also, both carriers and non-carriers showed worries about relatives who opted to not pursue genetic testing [62,70]. Untested women potentially at risk of HBOC presented less psychological distress and decisional conflicts when compared to their relatives who pursued genetic testing [81]. However, they were also less knowledgeable about potential risk factors and gene inheritance, besides reporting a greater perception of disease severity and controllability [81].

Positive and negative relational changes after genetic testing.

Applicants for HBOC and HNPCC reported feeling closer to their partners and siblings, while communication, support, and appreciation also improved for the other relatives. At the same time, applicants reported familial conflicts and difficult situations within the family context due to genetic testing [62]. A study comparing HBOC carriers and non-carriers found that perceptions of family expressiveness (the extent that family members are encouraged to act openly and express their feelings) decreased significantly more for carriers between the first genetic counseling session and 9 months after results [82]. In contrast, perceptions of family cohesion and family conflict did not differ significantly

between pathogenic variant carriers and non-carriers [82]. Interestingly, one study observed that in families with HBOC and HNPCC, an increase in the levels of family conflict after genetic testing predicted lower depression scores at 12 months [72].

Three reviewed studies indicate that pre-existing family functioning characteristics are predictors of the psychological adjustment of applicants [61,62,72]. HNPCC applicants who perceived lower family cohesion at pre-test, as well as a decrease in family cohesion six months after receiving the results, had higher depression scores one year after [72]. Also, applicants who perceived their nuclear families as disengaged or enmeshed at pre-test presented higher levels of hereditary cancer distress six months after test results [61]. They also experienced more adverse consequences in their relationships with partners and children, when compared to applicants who felt their families as moderately cohesive and adaptive [62].

The presence of the pathogenic variant in the extended family was also a predictor of the psychological adjustment of newly discovered pathogenic variant carriers. A study with 179 first and second-degree relatives of HNPCC pathogenic variant carriers found that a higher number of carriers (both in the immediate and extended family) predicted more depressive symptomatology in pathogenic variant carriers six months after the test result [73]. Cancer-related worries also tended to rise with the increase in the number of HNPCC carriers in the extended family and cancer-related distress and worry were higher when the proportion of carriers in the immediate family was low [73]. Discrepancies in cancer worry (when applicants had significantly different results in cancer worry at pre-test when compared to the family norm) also predicted higher depression scores 12 months after HNPCC results [72].

Siblings' adjustment.

Four studies included in this review focused specifically on the adjustment dynamics within sibships [64,83–85]. Smith et al. [85] assessed the psychological distress before and after genetic testing for BRCA1/2 in 212 sibships tested simultaneously. Distress was higher for both siblings when one sibling tested positive alone, and lower when results were positive for more than one sibling. Moreover, non-carrier siblings felt more distress when their siblings were carriers than when all siblings were non-carriers [85]. The importance of the pathogenic variant pattern among brothers and sisters was also found by Hamann et al. [84], who concluded that siblings who both tested positive for BRCA1/2 reported more friendly behavior towards each other than when only one sibling did. Also, Lodder et al. [64] found that non-carrier women who had a sister recently identified with the BRCA 1/2 pathogenic variant presented higher levels of depression at post-test than other non-carrier women. Furthermore, a study with 65 sisters of HBOC families found that non-carriers experienced similar levels of perceived risk, cancer worry, anxiety, and somatization as carriers [83].

Couples' adjustment.

Thirteen studies focused on the adjustment process to test results within the couple [64–69,73,75,77,79,86–88]. Cross-over effects in the couple were observed. That is, emotional states in one member of the couple were found to affect the adjustment of the other. Partner's distress was correlated with the level of distress reported by women at risk of developing breast/ovarian cancer [68]. High levels of partner support reported by HBOC carriers before taking the test significantly predicted lower levels of pathogenic variant carriers' distress up to two years after the test [77]. On the other hand, perceived partner anxiety predicted pathogenic variant carrier distress in the same time frame [77]. Importantly, effect sizes were stronger when pathogenic variant carriers perceived their partners as both unsupportive and anxious before testing, which predicted clinical distress levels up to two

years after testing [77]. In another study focusing on BRCA 1/2 couples, applicants reported less general and cancer-specific distress six months after test results when their partners had shared concerns and had provided effective support before genetic testing [79]. Moreover, low perceived partner support and partner avoiding talking about worries to protect the partner (protective buffering) predicted higher general distress in the applicant [79].

However, some applicants actively avoid partner support. Oostrom et al. [62] found that some applicants react to a positive pathogenic variant test by trying to emotionally distance themselves from their partners to protect and prepare them for the possibility of developing cancer or dying for it.

Six studies reported on the impact of the pathogenic variant in the partner and the couple's relationship [65,67,68,71,79,88]. Partners of HBOC pathogenic variant carriers experienced genetic testing as a stressful situation and considered this new medical condition to exacerbate pre-existing couple relationship problems [67]. These partners indicated that they would need more support, but they did not search for it because they were focused on helping their applicant spouses [67]. Some partners also mentioned discomfort about sharing worries with their spouses [67,79], because they did not want to overburden them. Therefore, the couple did not share their preoccupations, which often led applicants to think their partners were not sufficiently caring [65,67]. In this context, partners reported significant relationship strain [79], less couple intimacy, more frequent discussions about the future [88], and a sense of urgency regarding the pursuit of couples' life goals [67]. In contrast, open communication about cancer risk within the couple was found to be related to less distress in partners of women at risk for developing breast/ovarian cancer [68]. Some BRCA 1/2 partners reported that they became more involved in their spouses' families, talked more about cancer risk with the pathogenic variant carrier [88], and felt closer to their spouses after genetic testing [65]. Also, some partners of HNPCC pathogenic variant carriers, as well as

partners of not-yet-tested HNPCC individuals, did not perceive their partners' medical condition as personally relevant, even if their children also were at risk of carrying the pathogenic variant [71].

Findings from two studies suggest that approaching cancer risk as a team may be beneficial for the couple's adjustment [67,69]. It was found a significant positive association between dyadic consensus (the extent to which couples agree on important matters for the relationship) and levels of perceived support in couples dealing with HBOC risk. Higher scores for support and team approach were significantly associated with the couple's satisfaction [69]. Another study with HBOC families found that dealing with cancer risk as a team facilitates psychological adjustment, along with more active participation from partners in decision-making processes, greater satisfaction with their role as a supporter, and optimism [67]. However, the positive effect of dealing with cancer risk as a team was not confirmed by Shapira et al. [87] who did not find a significant association between dyadic coping and psychological adaptation in women identified with the BRCA 1/2 pathogenic variant.

The family system facing risk-reduction decision making and long-term managing of cancer risk

Six studies [14,57,63,71,76,87] specifically focused on family participation in risk reduction decision-making processes and long-term adjustment to life with genetic cancer risk. A qualitative study with heterogeneous hereditary cancer risk population found that family members generally communicated during involvement in genetic counseling and adopted open communication within the nuclear family and first-degree relatives but reported more difficulty in informing extended family relatives due to emotional distance [57]. Moreover, BRCA1/2 pathogenic variant carriers interviewed by Puski et al. [14] reported that having witnessed family members' experience of being diagnosed and treated for HBOC

represented a stimulus to be pro-active and to opt for risk-reducing surgery. They considered helpful gaining information about the surgical process, healing time, and side effects from family members who had already gone through a mastectomy or an oophorectomy [14]. The participants reported that while non-carrier relatives gave support by validating decisions, pathogenic variant carriers provided camaraderie and instilled hope and reassurance by sharing their experience [14]. However, two participants reported adverse effects of the support given by relatives who either tried to persuade them to undergo the surgical procedure when they did not want to or expressed disapproval when they intended to do the surgery [14].

Two studies found that risk management decisions had a significant impact on the process of adaptation to life with increased cancer risk, both for the pathogenic variant carriers and for their partners [63,87]. One study [87] discovered that women who underwent a risk-reducing mastectomy and their partners reported significantly higher levels of psychological adaptation to BRCA1/2 than women who did not. The other study [86] explored the long-term psychological impact of either regular breast cancer surveillance or prophylactic surgery and found that open communication within the nuclear family (partner and children) and with the family of origin (parents and siblings) four to nine years after genetic testing results was significantly associated with less breast-cancer-related distress in BRCA 1/2 pathogenic variant carriers [63]. Open communication with family members also significantly mediated the positive effect of social support on general and breast cancer specific distress. In other words, women who felt supported by their families were more likely to talk openly about hereditary cancer with their close relatives (e.g., partner, children, parents, and siblings), which in turn promoted their psychological adjustment [63].

Regarding the risk management of unaffected non-carriers, those that belong to BRCA1/2 families report overscreening behaviors, even though these were not recommended

[89]. These overscreening behaviors were correlated to a higher feeling of self-vulnerability and to higher comparative pessimism (e.g., tendency to think that negative events will more likely happen to oneself than to others), but not to higher anxiety levels [58].

Parents and children facing hereditary cancer risk

Three studies reported on the experience of being a parent in a family identified with hereditary cancer syndromes [76,80,90]. Two of three studies focused on the impact that poor communication might have on children of parents who are pathogenic variant carriers [76,90]. A qualitative study [76] involving five families with HBOC showed that parents found it difficult to talk with their children about cancer risk or downplayed the importance of the information and postponed disclosing their status. Consequently, children ended up learning about the familial cancer risk in an informal manner, without really understanding its meaning and consequences [76]. Children's inaccurate cancer risk perception and poor health literacy were also found by Patenaude et al. [80]. Some adult daughters of BRCA1/2 pathogenic variant carriers were not aware that they could be at a higher risk for cancer because their mothers were pathogenic variant carriers. Also, they did not know that if a woman carries the pathogenic variant, her sister has a 50% probability of being a carrier, and they were unaware of the importance of undergoing genetic testing to prevent cancer onset [80]. The parental influence on children's future health behavior was evident in HBOC families, where it was observed that daughters made the same choice their pathogenic variant carriers' mothers did, both regarding genetic testing and risk management measures [76].

Difficulties in communicating about cancer risk with their children also affected pathogenic variant carriers significantly [90]. In a study by Mays et al. [90] poor parent-child communication before genetic testing predicted greater distress in mothers one month after receiving their HBOC test results [90]. Interdependent effects of parenting dynamics were

also reported in women at risk of HBOC and their partners. More specifically, high levels of pre-test individual uncertainty regarding how to communicate test results to children in one-parent significantly predicted increased distress in the other member of the couple, up to one month after test results [90].

One study reported that some adult descendants of HBOC carriers viewed the likelihood of being a pathogenic variant carrier as an intense experience, eliciting internal conflicts and emotional pain [80]. Although most daughters in this study did not perceive themselves as less healthy because their mothers were carriers, others revealed deep fears and concerns regarding the possibility of carrying the pathogenic variant. These included worrying about their psychological health, pessimistic and paranoid thoughts, as well as fear of having to change life plans, particularly regarding childbearing. Moreover, some of these daughters were worried about transmitting the pathogenic variant to their children or not living long enough to see them grow up. Many expressed the intention of undergoing genetic testing as soon as possible, but others refused to be tested; the majority expressed ambivalence [80].

Discussion

This systematic review intended to synthesize how families with pathogenic variant carriers unaffected by cancer adjust to genetic testing results and life-saving risk management programs offered in the context of cancer genetic counseling. Taken together, the findings reveal a complex panorama where the systemic nature of family adjustment is evident. The diagnosis of a hereditary cancer syndrome in an unaffected individual works as a collective stressor, affecting not only the applicant but also their family. As posited by Daly [20], the hereditary cancer syndrome goes from generation to generation impacting each family member and the entire family, because “a positive genetic test would challenge the family

identity” (p. 549). As such, family members who are carriers may experience depression, anxiety, and distress due to fear of developing cancer and dying from it, or concerns about transmitting the pathogenic variant to their children. Moreover, non-carrier relatives may feel guilty towards family members affected by a pathogenic variant or cancer disease, thus experiencing a particular kind of “survivor guilt” [91] (p. 321). Survivor guilt can be considered a distressing experience where individuals blame themselves for being the ones to survive a life-threatening situation or disease [91]. It is common in trauma [91] and cancer survivors [92], and it can pose a significant threat to families’ well-being and systemic functioning as it may lead to relational distancing within the family. Nevertheless, a diagnosis of a hereditary cancer syndrome can also bring positive changes. Findings show that being a pathogenic variant carrier seems to bring a particular sense of connection and togetherness with other carriers in the family, possibly due to sharing similar distressing experiences [93]. This translates to relational changes in several sub-systems. Some family members might experience greater closeness, improved communication patterns, and supportive dynamics, while others might face conflicts and difficult situations [62].

Reviewed studies also highlighted that pathogenic variant carriers may adjust differently to positive genetic testing results, depending on the history and presence of the syndrome in the nuclear and extended family[73]. These findings are in line with the Family Systems Illness model (FSI; [19]), which is increasingly applied in the context of genomic disorders as a theoretical framework for understanding family challenges. According to this model, successful or dysfunctional family adaptation depends on the psychosocial demands of the disorder and the family functioning, and the resources used to cope with this stressor by the family members. This family adaptation seems to be particularly important at the level of close relationships: relationships between siblings, partners, and children. Selected studies provided evidence of better individual adjustment to the result of genetic testing when

siblings have the same results, even if they test positive. Furthermore, both carrier and non-carrier siblings appear to experience similar levels of perceived risk, cancer worry, anxiety, and somatization [83], revealing the adjustment processes to be interdependent. Regarding the partners of pathogenic variant carriers, although some of them did not consider the medical condition of their partners as personally relevant [71], others viewed genetic testing as a stressful event that seems to exacerbate previous problems in the romantic relationship [67]. Some partners described their need for support. However, their role as caregiver and support provider to their partner led them not to share their feelings and concerns [67]. In addition, the couple faces a central distressing difficulty in sharing genetic risk information with their children and in dealing with their reactions. For the children, the likelihood of also being a pathogenic variant carrier appeared as an intense experience they needed to adjust to [80]. To this end, children stressed the importance of more accurate information about genetic risk and what it entails, so that they could make informed decisions about their health and future life plans. This review recognized the parents' difficulties and children's need for information that led Werner-Lin et al. [94] to develop a set of recommendations for healthcare professionals to facilitate parents' decisions and disclosure processes for their school-aged children, adolescents, and young adults, according to their developmental abilities.

Family functioning and adjustment to a positive genetic test result and risk management behaviors of a pathogenic variant carrier also influenced the psychological adjustment and decision-making of new carriers. Some family dynamics (e.g., lower levels of family cohesion, disengagement, enmeshment) before and after genetic testing were associated with individuals' depression [72], higher levels of cancer distress, and worse relationships with partners and children [61] after receiving test results. The reviewed studies provided strong evidence for the impact of the partner's adjustment on the pathogenic variant

carrier's long-term fine-tuning to the hereditary cancer syndromes. For example, communication about the syndrome was hindered when carriers felt their partners as not supportive, not involved, or not attuned to their suffering, and thus preferred to cope with the stressful situation alone [67,71]. In contrast, open communication and approaching cancer as a team was associated with better adjustment [67,68]. This is in line with a previous review in which the interaction between couple members influences each other's distress [30]. Also, in studies with couples facing cancer, couples may act as systems, not just as individuals [95].

Although the literature is scarce, our review suggests that pathogenic variant carriers followed the example of their family members for deciding in terms of genetic testing and risk-management options. Family members might have a positive influence s on individual decisions and risk management behavior of those carrying a pathogenic variant, functioning as role models and by sharing first-hand experiences or as interlocutors to talk thus supporting the decision-making process. Testimonials and active encouragement from family members might also provide valuable information to help potential applicants decide whether to undergo genetic testing and other preventive measures [14,96]. Nevertheless, relatives might also function as a source of biased information or contribute to additional distress when they insist on trying to persuade pathogenic variant carriers to make certain decisions, making them feel challenged in their self-determination[14].

Support received from family members was recognized, by both non-carriers and carriers, as important in dealing with the challenges posed by their condition. Emotional support in families with hereditary cancer, in which multiple members simultaneously provide and receive support from relatives, was characterized as communal coping processes [83,97], as previously identified in individuals with other chronic conditions [98]. The positive effect of family support on distress seems to be explained by the use of an open communication between family members [63]. However, communication may be hindered by

protective buffering processes: pathogenic variant carriers may refrain from sharing their concerns for fear of aggravating the distress of their close relatives or may emotionally slip away from their partners to help them better prepare for the eventuality of their death from cancer [62]. Recognition of this dimension has already been recognized in previous studies, leading to the development of interventions specifically aimed to improve family communication about hereditary cancer and genetic testing [99].

Limitations of the current research

Most of the selected studies focused on the psychological adjustment of families with inherited hereditary breast and ovarian cancer risk and HNPCC risk. Only one study explored the emotional response and role of the family in the decision-making process of positive mutation carriers of other syndromes (Familial Adenomatous Polyposis). This may reflect a gap in the literature on the topic, but also that our search entailed a syntax that was not broad enough to encompass other hereditary cancer syndromes. Other medical terms may have been used in studies relating to other hereditary cancer syndromes. Also, not restricting studies by study design helped to aggregate existing knowledge but prevented a meta-analytical approach that could yield a more precise estimate of the strength of the findings.

Research gaps and recommendations for future studies and clinical practice

Our review identified four major research gaps. First, there is scarce knowledge about the psychological adaptation of children growing up in families with a known hereditary cancer syndrome. This calls for further research that explores how hereditary cancer affects psychological development and health behaviors of children and adolescents, and how it should be managed to minimize negative impacts. Another major gap concerns the lack of research focused on long-term adjustment phases of risk management. Little is known about

how best to involve family members at critical turning points in risk-reduction decision-making and their adjustment to the consequences of those decisions over time. In this process, it's important to consider the limits and possible contraindications of family involvement. Such knowledge is critical to empower the family to use its resources for mutual support.

A third gap concerns the lack of cancer genetic health literacy interventions for both applicants and their relatives on the following topics: the multiple psychological impacts of hereditary cancer risk on applicants, their biological relatives, and partners; the expected impact on relationships and how to overcome it; the importance of family self-supportive dynamics (e.g., open communication), and the common difficulties associated with it (e.g., protective buffering, survivor guilt). Health literacy targeting close relatives from whom the carrier expects support, such as partners, might be more important in families without a clinical history of familial cancer, given the possible devaluation of the syndrome and the carrier's distress. Lastly, there is a lack of translational research towards family-centered genetic cancer risk care. The reviewed role of the family in the individual adjustment of pathogenic variant carriers calls for a debate about balancing the right to self-determination and individual privacy (e.g., the right not to involve the family in decision-making processes) with family-centered interventions. Hereditary cancer syndrome is a clinical condition in which several members of the same family are at different stages of diagnosis/risk management through interdependent adjustment processes and communal coping. Thus, interventions that target the family system and not just its members individually should be considered to better address the family's psychosocial and clinical needs. The few existing interventions, for example Multifamily Discussion Groups (MFDG) [21], have shown promising preliminary evidence on improvements in family relationships and psychological well-being.

Research should further focus on the multiple interrelated adjustment processes [15] to better capture the systemic nature of family adaptation. To this end, we provide four methodological recommendations. First, to include family members as informants. Most studies have used the applicant as the only data source, but it is important to examine the lived experience of family members, especially children and young people. Second, to examine the process of interdependent adjustment of family members (e.g., couples, siblings, parents-children subsystems) through dyadic or triadic study designs. Third, use longitudinal designs to examine family dynamics and adjustment trajectories. Studies should consider the major family events expected in the course of hereditary cancer syndromes including the pathogenic variant carrier or a family member developing cancer; the pathogenic variant carrier or a family member undergoing prophylactic surgery; the pathogenic variant carrier reaching a critical age (e.g., the age at which the index case was diagnosed with cancer); the pathogenic variant carrier becoming a parent; a child of the pathogenic variant carrier reaching a critical age (e.g., the age at which they must decide whether or not to be tested); or the death of a family member diagnosed with cancer. Lastly, the active involvement of pathogenic variant carriers and their families in research using participatory approaches would ensure that research focus on topics that are relevant to patients and close to their daily experiences. Moreover, this may contribute not only to inform health professionals and improve care practices, but also to increase people's participation and adherence to treatment.

Conclusion

Our review is the first describing family members' adjustment to genetic testing and risk management, and the influence of this adjustment on the psychological response and risk management decisions and behaviors of pathogenic variant carriers. Our findings provide valuable evidence regarding the interdependent adjustment processes of family members to

the increased risk of developing cancer. Three family members emerged as particularly important for adult pathogenic variant carriers' coping with the inherited genetic pathogenic variant: siblings, romantic partners, and children. In fact, hereditary cancer syndrome is a familial health condition, and a positive genetic testing result in a person might have implications for their close and extended relatives. Their relationships change, and pre-existing family functioning may not only affect the adjustment of the newly diagnosed pathogenic variant carrier overtime but may also subsequently affect the adherence to genetic testing and the health behavior of other relatives. It is therefore important to educate and support healthcare professionals in identifying key strengths and weaknesses in individual and family adjustment for the provision of family-centered care.

Table 1: Characteristics of the included studies

Author, year	Country	Design	GT	Sample size (n)	Age (yrs) mean (SD), range	Gender MALE - n(%) : FEMALE - n(%)
Ashida et al., 2009	USA	Longitudinal cohort study	HBOC	178	39.77(14.75), 18-83	75(42.1%):103(57.9%)
Bartle-Haring et al., 2003	USA	Longitudinal observational (pilot) study	HBOC or HNPCC	50:MC=25; FM=25	MC=39.8; FM=40.8	MC=5(20%):19(76%); FM=9(36%):14(56%)
den Heijer et al., 2011	NLD	Longitudinal observational	HBOC	222	47.1(8.3), 29–68	F=100%
Di Prospero et al., 2001	CAN	Exploratory study	HBOC	24	52.9, 31-77	2(8.3%):22(91.7%)
Douma et al., 2011	NLD	Cross-sectional	FAP	FM=129	FM=46.1 (11.5), 21-79	63 (49%):66 (51%)
Eliezer et al., 2014	USA	Longitudinal observational	HNPCC	179 (26 families)	39, 18-72	75(42%):104(58%)
Hamann et al., 2008	USA	Experimental	HBOC	98 (49 dyads:16 with positive results, 13 with negative results and 20 with mixed results)	TotalMean=47.72(12.99)	23(23.5%):75(76.5%)
Katapodi et al., 2011	USA	Descriptive, Cross-sectional	HBOC	372 (MC= 200; FM=172)	51(11), 22–83	F=100%
Koehly et al., 2008	USA	Cross-sectional	HBOC	65 (31 families)	40.7(8.6)	F=100%
Lodder et al., 2001	NLD	Longitudinal observational	HBOC	154 (MC=78 FM=56)	MC=38.4; FM=38.7	F=100%
Manne et al., 2004	USA	Longitudinal observational	HBOC	464 (MC=212; FM=252)	MC=50(10.76), 27–75; FM=54, 29-79	MC_F=100%; FM=117(99.2%):1(0.8%)
Mauer et al., 2015	USA	Cross-sectional	HBOC	FM=25	FM=38.5, 24-55	
Mays et al., 2014	USA	Prospective study	HBOC	109 dyads	FM_Mothers:45.9 (6.1); FM_partners:47.8 (6.9)	FM_Mothers:F=100%; FM_Partners:M=100%
McInerney-Leo et al., 2005	USA	Prospective study	HBOC	262	TotalMean=40	Total=92(35%):170(65%)
Mendes & Sousa, 2012	PT	Exploratory, qualitative study	HNPCC or HBOC or	50 (9 families)	NR	F=58%

			HDGC				
Metcalf et al., 2002	CAN	Cross-sectional	HBOC	FM=59	FM=50.6, 28-73	M=100%	
Milhabet et al., 2013	FR	Cross-sectional	HBOC	FM=77	FM=32.09(5.21)	F=100%	
Mireskandari et al., 2006	AUS	Exploratory study	HBOC	FM=15	41.4, 30-56	M=100%	
Mireskandari et al., 2007	AUS	Single-assessment study design	HBOC	190 (MC=95; FM=95)	MC=45.4(10.2), 23-72; FM=42.9(9.4), 23-67	95(50%):95(50%)	
Murakami et al., 2004	JAP	Prospective qualitative study	HNPCC	47 (MC=31; FM=16)	TotalMean=47(10), 28-60	Total=20(47.6%):22(52.4%)	
Norris et al., 2009	USA	Descriptive qualitative study	HBOC	17 (5 families)	NR	6(35.3%):11(64,7%)	
Patenaude et al., 2013	USA	Observational	HBOC	MC=40	FM=21, 18-24	F=100%	
Peterson et al., 2003	USA	Retrospective, cross-sectional, qualitative study	HNPCC	39 (5 families)	TotalMean=49.2, 21-81	15(38.5%):24(61.5%)	
Puski et al., 2018	USA	Qualitative descriptive	HBOC	20	20-50	F=100%	
Shapira et al., 2017	USA	Observational	HBOC	229 (MC=168; FM=61)	TotalMean=39.7(10.1)	NR	
Smith et al., 1999	USA	Longitudinal observational	HBOC	212	TotalMean=46.32(16.72)	87(41%):125(59%)	
Van Oostrom et al., 2007a	NLD	Prospective study	HNPCC	MC=271	MC=43.25(12.7)	32(12%):239(88%)	
Van Oostrom et al., 2007b	NLD	Prospective study	HNPCC	MC=272	MC=43.25(12.7)	32(12%):239(88%)	
Watts et al., 2011	UK	Observational	HBOC	188 (MC=94; FM=94)	MC=42.9(9.4), 23-67; FM=45.4(10.2), 23-72	F=100% (FM_M=100%)	
Wylie et al., 2003	USA	Longitudinal observational	HBOC	203	TotalMean=45.27(13.67)	M=100%	

Table 1: Characteristics of the included studies (continue)

Author, year	MC Familiar role	FM	FM Gene Pathogenic variant Status	Follow-up points	Outcome:Measure	Quality
Ashida et al., 2009	NR	NR	Carrier-NonCarrier	T0: Baseline T1: 6 months after disclosure – T2: 12 months after disclosure	Depression:CES-D; Family relationships:FES; Cancer worry:ad hoc tool	5
Bartle-Haring et al., 2003	Siblings, spouses, or son/daughter	Siblings, spouses, or parents	Carrier	T1: baseline – T2: at disclosure	Distress:IES; Depression and anxiety:HSCL; Differentiation of Self:DSI	4
den Heijer et al., 2011	Daughter, partner, mother, friend	NR	Carrier	T0: baseline – T1: 2 months	Distress:IES; Depression and anxiety:HADS; Social support:MSPSS	5
Di Prospero et al., 2001	Parents, partner	Partner, sons	NonCarrier	NR	Cancer risk perception; worry about cancer; attitudes toward surveillance and prevention options; satisfaction with clinical services; additional support - satisfaction of having taken genetic test:ad hoc tool	4
Douma et al., 2011	Partner	Partner	NonCarrier	NR	Cancer Worry: CWS, Intrusion: IES-Intrusion subscale, and Quality of Life: SF36 Health Survey	5
Eliezer et al., 2014	Partner, son, parent, cousin, uncle	Internal and external family	Carrier-NonCarrier	T0: baseline (genetic test) – T1: 6 months (test results delivered 1-2 months from baseline)	Distress:IES; Cancer worry and Depression:ad hoc tool	4
Hamann et al., 2008	Sibling	Sibling	Carrier-NonCarrier	NR	Circumplex measures:SAS-C, IMI-C; Anger and anxiety:STAI	5
Koehly et al., 2008	Sister	Sister	Carrier-NonCarrier	NR	Distress:BSI; Cancer worry:LCWS; Cancer risk perception:PRI; Social integration, reciprocity and shared support:ad hoc tool	5
Lodder et al., 2001	Partner	Partner	NonCarrier	T0: pre-test – T1: post-test	Depression and anxiety:HADS; Distress:IES	4
Manne et al., 2004	Partner	Partner	NonCarrier	T0: pre-test – T1: 6 months after disclosure	Partner Response to Cancer:PRCI; Distress:IES; Depression and anxiety:BSI-Anxiety and Depression subscales; Partner support; Relationship strain; Sharing of concerns:ad hoc tool	4

Mauer et al., 2015	Partner	Partner	NonCarrier	NR	Male attitudes towards partnership and sexuality:ad hoc tool	4
Mays et al., 2014	Mothers	Partner	Carrier-NonCarrier	T0: baseline – T1: 1 month after disclosure	Distress:BSI; Parent-Adolescent Communication:PAC; Decisional conflict:DCS.	5
McInerney-Leo et al., 2005	NR	NR	NonCarrier	T0: baseline – T1: 6 months – T2: 9 months	Family Relationship Index:FRI; Family Environment:FES	4
Mendes & Sousa, 2012	NR	NR	Carrier-NonCarrier	NR	Familial experience of genetic counseling and meaning, impacts and management of the genetic condition: ad hoc semi-structured interview; The personal relevance of the family interview: post-interview questionnaire, ad hoc tool	
Metcalfe et al., 2002	Partner	Partner	NonCarrier	NR	NR	5
Milhabet et al., 2013	NR	NR	NonCarrier	NR	Screening behaviors: ad hoc tool; State anxiety: STAI-YA; Feelings of self-vulnerability or self-risk perception: ad hoc tool; Comparative perception of risk or comparative optimism	
Mireskandari et al., 2006	Partner	Partner	NonCarrier	NR	NR	5
Mireskandari et al., 2007	Partner	Partner	NonCarrier	NR	Monitoring attentional style:MBSS; Distress, Depression and anxiety:DASS and IES; Information and support needs; Knowledge about breast/ovarian cancer; Individual and couple factors; Cancer-related event in the family:ad hoc tool.	5
Murakami et al., 2003	NR	NR	NonCarrier	T0: pre-test – T1: administration genetic test – T2: 1 month after test	Depression:SCID; Personality factors:EPQR; Feelings of guilt:ad hoc tool	5
Norris et al., 2009	Mothers and wives	Sons and husbands	NonCarrier	NR	Communication and decision-making strategies:ad hoc Semi-structured Interview	5
Katapodi et al., 2011	NR	NR	Relatives did not pursue testing	NR	Illness appraisals of HBOC: Breast/Ovarian cancer risk factor knowledge index; IPQ-R; ad hoc tool; Psychological distress: ad hoc tool; Family environment: Family problem solving and communication index; Family relationships inventory; Decisional Conflict: Decisional conflict scale	

Patenaude et al., 2013	Mothers	Daughters	Carrier-NonCarrier	NR	General distress: BSI-18; Cancer related distress: IES; Breast Cancer Genetic Counselling Knowledge: BCKQ	5
Peterson et al., 2003	NR	NR	Carrier-NonCarrier	NR	Personal perceptions and persuasion in motivating:ad hoc Semi-structured Interview	5
Puski et al., 2018	NR	Not specified	Carrier	NR	Decision-making:ad hoc Semi-structured Interview	5
Shapira et al., 2017	Partner	Partner	NonCarrier	NR	Psychological adaptation:PAS; Dyadic coping:DCI; Risk perception:ad hoc tool;	5
Smith et al., 1999	Sibling	Siblings	Carrier	T0: baseline, before genetic testing – T1: 1/2 weeks after receiving results	Distress:IES, STAI	5
Van Oostrom et al., 2007a	NR	NR	Carrier-NonCarrier	T0: baseline – T1: 1 week – T2: 6 months after disclosure	Distress:IES; Anxiety and Depression:HADS; Nuclear family functioning:FACES; Differentiation to parents:DFSC; Familial communication style:ODHCFS; Perceived social support:ad hoc tool; Cancer worry:CWS.	5
Van Oostrom et al., 2007b	NR	NR	Carrier-NonCarrier	T0: baseline – T1: 1 week – T2: 6 months after disclosure	Distress:IES; Anxiety and Depression:HADS; Nuclear family functioning:FACES; Differentiation to parents:DFSC; Familial communication style:ODHCFS; Perceived social support:ad hoc tool; Cancer worry:CWS.	5
Watts et al., 2011	Partner	Partner	NonCarrier	NR	Distress:DASS, IES; Dyadic adjustment:DAS; Support and team approach:ad hoc tool.	5
Wylie et al., 2003	Partner	Partner	Carrier-NonCarrier	T0: baseline – T1: 1 week – T2: 4 months – T3: 1 year – T4: 2 years after disclosure	Distress:IES; Spousal anxiety/distress; Family cancer history; Carrier status:ad hoc tool	5

Legend: NR = Not reported | AUS = Australia; CAN = Canada; JAP = Japan; NLD = The Nederland; UK = The United Kingdom; USA = The United states of America; PT = Portugal | GT = Genetic test; HNPCC = Hereditary nonpolyposis colorectal cancer; HBOC = Hereditary breast and ovarian cancer syndrome | FM = family member; MC = pathogenic variant carrier | RMB = Risk management behaviours | BSI = Brief Symptom Inventory; CES-D = Center for Epidemiology Studies; CWS = Cancer Worry Scale; DAS = Dyadic Adjustment Scale; DASS = Depression, Anxiety, and Stress Scale; DCI = Dyadic Coping Inventory; : DCS = Decision Conflict Scale DFSS = Differentiation

in the Family System Scale; DFSC = Decision Conflict Scale; DSI = Differentiation of Self Inventory; EPQ-R = Eysenck Personality Questionnaire; FACES = Family Adaptability and Cohesion Evaluation Scales; FES = Family Environment Scale; FRI = Family Relationship Index; HADS = Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale; MSPSS = Multidimensional Scale of Perceived Social Support; HSCL = Hopkins Symptom Checklist; IES = Impact of Events Scale; IMI-C = Impact Message Inventory—Circumplex; LCWS = Lerman Cancer Worry Scale; MBSS = Miller Behavioural Style Scale; NEO-FFI = NEO-Five Factor Inventory; ODHCFs = Openness to Discuss; HCFS = Hereditary Cancer in the Family Scale; PAC = Parent-Adolescent Communication; PAS = Psychological Adaptation Scale; PRCI = Partner Response to Cancer Inventory; SAS-C = Support Actions Scale-Circumplex; STAI = Stait-Trait Personality Inventory; SCID = Structured Clinical Interview | 5 = 100% quality criteria met; 4 = 80% quality criteria met.

Supplemental Data

The supplemental data includes one table: Supplementary material 1 (S1) – Evaluation of quality of selected records according to the mixed-methods appraisal tool checklist (MMAT-v2018)

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Declaration of Interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

Author's Contributions

Célia Sales, Paula Mena Matos, and Giada Pietrabissa conceptualized the study. Giada Pietrabissa and Vanessa Bertuzzi conducted the first systematic searches in electronic databases. Pedro Gomes and Célia Sales conducted the hand searches and Pedro Gomes and Maria Neves conducted the search update in electronic databases. All co-authors collaborated in the selection of papers, quality appraisal and extraction data. Pedro Gomes, Giada Pietrabissa and Célia Sales wrote the original draft and all co-authors reviewed and contributed to the writing of the final version of the manuscript.

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Figure titles and legends

Title: *Figure 1*. PRISMA Flow-chart

Legend: Flowchart representing the number of records at each time of the systematic review process.

Table titles and legends

Title: *Table 1*. Characteristics of the included studies

Legend: NR = Not reported | AUS = Australia; CAN = Canada; JAP = Japan; NLD = The Nederland; UK = The United Kingdom; USA = The United states of America | GT = Genetic test; HNPCC = Hereditary nonpolyposis colorectal cancer; HBOC = Hereditary breast and ovarian cancer syndrome | FM = family member; MC = mutation carrier | RMB = Risk management behaviours | BSI = Brief Symptom Inventory; CES-D = Center for Epidemiology Studies; CWS = Cancer Worry Scale; DAS = Dyadic Adjustment Scale; DASS = Depression, Anxiety, and Stress Scale; DCI = Dyadic Coping Inventory; : DCS = Decision Conflict Scale DFSS = Differentiation in the Family System Scale; DFSC = Decision Conflict Scale; DSI = Differentiation of Self Inventory; EPQ-R = Eysenck Personality Questionnaire; FACES = Family Adaptability and Cohesion Evaluation Scales; FES = Family Environment Scale; FRI = Family Relationship Index; HADS = Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale; MSPSS = Multidimensional Scale of Perceived Social Support; HSCL = Hopkins Symptom Checklist; IES = Impact of Events Scale; IMI-C = Impact Message Inventory—Circumplex; LCWS = Lerman Cancer Worry Scale; MBSS = Miller Behavioural Style Scale; NEO-FFI = NEO-Five Factor Inventory; ODHCFS = Openness to Discuss; HCFS = Hereditary Cancer in the Family Scale; PAC = Parent-Adolescent Communication; PAS = Psychological Adaptation Scale; PRCI = Partner Response to Cancer Inventory; SAS-C = Support Actions Scale-Circumplex; STAI = Stait-

Trait Personality Inventory; SCID = Structured Clinical Interview; IPQR = Revised Illness Perception Questionnaire | 5 = 100% quality criteria met; 4 = 80% quality criteria met.